

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results - Update

DELIVERABLE 8.4

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ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract

This document provides an update to the OPERAS-PLUS project’s plan for exploitation and dissemination of results, including further details on its Key Exploitable Results (KERs). It describes the definition, value proposition, IP management, exploitation path and dissemination activities and adoption methodology of each KER to be sustained beyond the life of the project. This is the first update of the PEDR plan with a final version to be provided at M30.

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Executive summary

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure dedicated to support open scholarly communication for the Social Sciences and the Humanities in the European Research Area (ERA). Designed as a distributed infrastructure, it entered into its preparatory phase and was incorporated as an AISBL (Belgian non-profit Association) in 2019. OPERAS was included as part of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) roadmap in 2021¹ and is now on its path to become operational as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)² in 2028 thanks to the support of the OPERAS-PLUS project.

A key objective within the OPERAS-PLUS project is the dissemination and exploitation of project results. The first version of the OPERAS-PLUS Dissemination and exploitation plan (PEDR) was designed to describe the overall methodology as a guideline for the activities of all project partners when sharing information about the project, engaging with the community, reaching out to it as well as the activities to be carried out to enhance the successful exploitation of the project results.

This updated version provides further details of the initial Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identified in the project preparation phase, and revised in the first months of the project:

1. KER1 – OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework
2. KER2 – OPERAS Innovation Lab
3. KER3 – OPERAS portfolio of services
4. KER4 – OPERAS user training framework
5. KER5 – OPERAS national nodes

OPERAS is a distributed infrastructure with many different services and activities, thus has the challenge of addressing the added value for all its stakeholders including internal (e.g. its members), external (e.g. SSH researchers, policy makers), a mix of both internal and external (e.g. projects, national consortia), and users of services (e.g. SSH researchers, authors, editors, libraries). Therefore, to reach these diverse stakeholders, different strategies need to be used such as tailoring the types of publications and material (i.e. scientific publications, policy briefs, blog posts), public events (i.e. conferences, workshops, webinars), as well as the channels (i.e. website, social media).

Each of the KERs has been assigned a "KER champion" to act as the central contact point for all issues that might arise related to this KER with content being managed via

¹ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/>

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Research_Infrastructure_Consortium

the OPERAS-PLUS project information management system using Confluence.

Sustainability for each Key Exploitable Result has started to be assessed covering organisational, technical and financial aspects that are supported by the wider OPERAS quality and service management implementation based on the FitSM and ISO 9001 standards.

The OPERAS-PLUS dissemination and exploitation plan pulls together defined target audiences matched with tailored dissemination strategies and measures that combine specific key results and how each will be exploited. Further refinements and detailed plans will be made over the course of the project and reported on in a final future update.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Overview and document structure

The dissemination and exploitation of project results are essential steps in the research and development process. The OPERAS-PLUS “Dissemination and exploitation plan” (PEDR) is designed to describe the overall methodology across the OPERAS-PLUS project as a guideline for the activities of all project partners when sharing information about the project, engaging with the community, reaching out to it as well as the activities to be carried out to enhance the successful exploitation of the project results. The plan identifies the strategy for dissemination and exploitation and describes the various channels that the project uses for it. This plan is complemented by the communications strategy outlined in D8.1.

The PEDR is to be considered a living document. This current document is the first update from the first draft of the PEDR (D8.3) and will have a final update at the end of the final reporting period (M30).

Overall, a successful exploitation and dissemination plan will ensure that the results of the project are widely available and can be used to their full potential, contributing to the advancement of knowledge and the development of new products and services.

Therefore, this document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: introduces the document and its structure.
- Section 2: details the approach to exploitation along with updated descriptions, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and activities plans for each of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- Section 3: provides an update on overall project KPIs as well as the services used to measure the success of the communication and dissemination measures.
- Section 4: concludes the overall document.
- Annex: provides draft information for each KER in order to submit formal entries in the Horizon Results Booster platform.

1.2. OPERAS-PLUS Results

In a programme guide by Horizon Europe³, the term “results” is defined as follows:

What is generated during the project implementation. This may include, for

³

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide-horizon_en.pdf

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example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works, etc) are 'Intellectual Property', which may, if appropriate, be protected by formal 'Intellectual Property Rights'. Example: Successful large-scale demonstrator: trial with 3 airports of an advanced forecasting system for proactive airport passenger flow management).

There will be a number of individual results produced by OPERAS-PLUS, that will each be tracked and continually analysed for identification of appropriate exploitation strategies, but overall, the project will focus on identifying and articulating Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The initial KERs identified in the project preparation phase, and revised in the first months of the project, are summarised below, with further details on each are provided in Section 2 and the initial draft of the Horizon Results template in the Annex:

1. KER1 - OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework
2. KER2 - OPERAS Innovation Lab
3. KER3 - OPERAS portfolio of services
4. KER4 - OPERAS user training framework
5. KER5 - OPERAS national nodes

2. Exploitation

Exploitation means the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including inter alia, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

2.1. Approach

For clarity for both consortium members as well as external stakeholders, it is important to distinguish between project results and key exploitable results.

2.1.1. Project results

As mentioned, project results are generated during the project implementation. This may include know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. They also include research roadmaps, policy recommendations, reports, platforms

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(collaboration), skills and knowledge, educational materials, codes of conduct, pre-standards, prototypes, software, publications and data.

2.1.2. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The primary project results from the dissemination and exploitation point of view are the Key Exploitable Results (KER). A specific note from the EC Portal states that before uploading a result in the Horizon Results Platform is it important to make sure that it is in fact a Key Exploitable Result. The EC Portal defines a KER as: "Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights".

Therefore, OPERAS-PLUS is prioritising the identification of the main results (as defined above), which have been selected and prioritised due to their high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use of and derive benefits from - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

The following criteria are used to select and prioritise these results:

- Degree of innovation
- Exploitability
- Impact

2.1.3. KER Champion

For further refining and consolidating the collection of information required to fully analyse, articulate and disseminate, each of the KERs has been assigned a "KER champion". The role of the KER champion is to act as the central contact point for all issues that might arise related to this KER. The champion also helps to coordinate and encourage the exploitation and dissemination of the KER. The champion also acts as the primary spokesperson for the KER and accepts or suggests changes and improvements of the KER-related documentation, promotional material, and plans in collaboration with the different WP8 team members.

2.1.4. Confluence

The OPERAS-PLUS project management has selected Confluence⁴ as the solution for its information management system to provide a full knowledge base. Confluence also offers a number of functionalities that support not only static collection of information, but also the management of several project activities such as deliverables and

⁴ <https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence>

milestones, action assignment as well as templates that can be used to harmonise content.

For management of both project objectives and KERs, a dedicated section of the project Confluence space has been assigned , with a template having already been structured based on the Horizon Results Platform required set of information (i.e. Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs; About us; Result Description and Influence; Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook; and Investors Corner).

This approach offers the information to be collaboratively worked on, always transparent in its availability, while ensuring that the right information can be easily imported into the portal by project’s end.

Title	KER #	KER Champion	KER Description	KER Full Name	Related WP#	Target Audience	Type
KER5 - OPERAS national nodes	KER5	@Delfim Leão		OPERAS national nodes	WP7 Support to national nodes		OTHER INTANGIBLE
KER4 - OPERAS user training framework	KER4	@Franjo Peñar		OPERAS user training framework	WP6 User engagement and training		TBD
KER3 - OPERAS portfolio of services	KER3	@Sy Holsinger		OPERAS portfolio of services	WP5 Technical support to OPERAS services		SERVICES
KER2 - OPERAS Innovation Lab	KER2	@Maciej Maryl		OPERAS Innovation Lab	WP4 OPERAS Innovation Lab development		SCIENTIFIC OR TECH R&D ICT SOFTWARE DIGITAL SOLUTION
KER1 - OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework	KER1	@Yannick Legré		OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework	WP2 OPERAS construction phase framework development		OTHER INTANGIBLE

Image 1: Screenshot of project results and KERs in Confluence

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Image 2: Screenshot of KER template in Confluence

2.1.5. Horizon results booster service

Several consortium partners have had experience from previous projects (i.e. TRIPLE) running through the Horizon Results Booster⁵ service that offers expert, free of charge, support services to boost the exploitation potential of research results, disseminate effectively, and go to market. There are 3 different modules offered: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy, Business Plan Development, and Go To Market.

It is expected that the initial use of the available templates will help KER Champions to better articulate their exploitation plans. A formal request of the service will be evaluated as the project develops.

2.1.6. IPR Management

Intellectual property management is the management of an organisation's intellectual property (IP), including patents, trademarks, copyrights, and trade secrets. The goal of IP management is to maximise the value of an organisation's IP while minimising the associated risks, costs, and administrative burdens. IP management activities include protecting IP, licensing and monetising IP, and leveraging IP to create new products and services.

The OPERAS-PLUS Consortium Agreement remains the reference document for

⁵ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

handling of IPR, whether as background or as foreground. However, any result of research, work, publication or invention that derives from the activities carried out within the scope of the OPERAS-PLUS project and is susceptible to economic exploitation or may give rise to a request for ownership of intellectual property rights, the project management (WP1) shall be notified including the beneficiary representative. IPR will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis as necessary.

In addition, IPR will be explicitly analysed as part of the KER business and sustainability model, but will be more of a focus in the final deliverable (D8.5 at M30).

2.1.7. Sustainability

The OPERAS-PLUS project is laying the groundwork for a sustainable future by establishing comprehensive frameworks across a number of different areas towards its goal of being an ERIC. Sustainability is a core component of the project's mission to support open scholarly communication in SSH across Europe for the years to come.

Each KER has been assigned a dedicated champion responsible for its sustainability and exploitation. These champions are tasked with ensuring that the KERs are not only relevant and valuable to the SSH community but also organisationally, financially and technically sustainable. This includes developing detailed sustainability plans for each KER that address each of these aspects.

As the sustainability of the OPERAS portfolio of services is a pivotal component to its long-term success, ensuring that the infrastructure remains relevant and beneficial to the SSH community is vital. This portfolio of services enhances visibility and accessibility across Europe, providing a robust platform for open scholarly communication. Continuous engagement with users and stakeholders drives the iterative improvement of services, ensuring they meet evolving needs and maintain high quality and relevance. This approach not only ensures the services' utility but also positions them for sustained impact and growth in the future, aligning with broader European research objectives and fostering a culture of open, collaborative scholarship.

It is important to note that OPERAS has 3 types of services as part of its portfolio: Managed, Community, and Internal:

- Managed services (e.g. GoTriple⁶) are when OPERAS is responsible for the overall service and coordination of the service delivery and evolution. This provides value when a sustainable structure is required and/or is strategic for OPERAS.
- Community services (e.g. PRISM⁷) are services that are discoverable from the

⁶ <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.doabooks.org/en/null/prism>

OPERAS website, but are managed directly by the community provider. This is valuable when there is a sustainable structure established and amplification along with direct OPERAS participation, contribution, and/or support is beneficial.

- Internal services are not orderable, but are necessary for managing or operating the OPERAS federation (e.g. OPERAS ID⁸). These comprise both technical and non-technical services that must still be managed though not requestable by those outside of the federation.

GoTriple is a perfect example of a managed service as it is aligned with OPERAS' mission to make Open Science a reality for research in SSH, while also benefiting from the legal entity established. The OPERAS AISBL provides solid legal and administrative support, along with the value add brought around dissemination, communication, community engagement, and service management support. The organisation between the OPERAS AISBL and the partners from the TRIPLE project⁹ has been formalised via the definition of a Memorandum of Understanding, including a Terms of Reference, which outlines both the management and coordination of the service as well as the commitment of the various partners to continue to actively contribute to maintaining and evolving the service and community.

In addition to the organisation aspects, in order to keep GoTriple technically sustainable after the project ends, we conducted a categorisation of GoTriple into service components with specifications of each comprising: type (enabling, enhancing), short description, service component provider, and technology readiness level (TRL). Within this activity, we identified 18 service components, provided by 12 different providers. Agreements are being established between OPERAS and each component provider (supplier) to ensure that each component will be provided beyond the life of the project. The names of the agreements will depend on the type of supplier (i.e. Operational Level Agreements with internal suppliers, Underpinning Agreements or Contracts with external suppliers). This agreement structure, methodology, and terminology follow the FitSM lightweight service management standard that is being used as the underlying framework.

An embedded activity as part of the IT service management implementation, and more specifically in Service Portfolio Management, is how any new or updated service is captured, assessed, and approved. This process is conducted through the use of Service Design and Transition Packages (SDTP). A core component of this structured SDTP document is the identification and articulation of appropriate business models that can

⁸ <https://id.operas-eu.org/>

⁹ <https://project.gotriple.eu/>

support the sustainability of the given services. This is just one example of how OPERAS' structure can potentially underpin any KER result from the project. Though it does not necessarily have to be the mechanism that is used, it represents the possibility for KER to be continuously exploited where needed.

2.2. Key Exploitable Results

As mentioned in Section 1, there have been and will be a number of individual results produced by OPERAS-PLUS, that are and will continue to be tracked and appropriate exploitation strategies analysed, but overall, the project focuses on Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The initial KERs identified in the project preparation phase, and revised in the first months of the project, are detailed in this section. Updated status and activity plans are also provided.

2.2.1. KER1 – OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework

This KER covers the overarching governance and sustainability of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure as it moves towards becoming an ERIC. Therefore the individual results are combined into a single KER with dedicated exploitation plans as follows:

- The compliance and/or certification of the OPERAS ERIC with quality, IT service and risk management ISO standards.
- An initial legal framework and financial multiannual plan to prepare for the transition towards an ERIC.
- Updated governance model, including relationships with private and commercial entities.
- Prototype and update of the Business Model to support the long-term sustainability of OPERAS.
- An equal opportunity pan-European employment framework with a specific focus on the gender equality plan, including the applicability of RESAVER¹⁰.
- Develop and implement a risk management framework and capacity plan.
- Update medium and long-term strategic plans.

KER1 Overview

KER #	KER1
KER Full Name	OPERAS core governance, finance, and management framework
KER Description	The OPERAS core governance, finance, and management

¹⁰ <https://www.resaver.eu/>

	Framework (KERI) encompasses the foundational elements necessary for transitioning OPERAS into a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). This KER includes the development and implementation of various frameworks such as governance, financial sustainability, human resources, risk management, and capacity planning. The aim is to ensure that OPERAS operates as a robust and sustainable research infrastructure, facilitating open scholarly communication within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).
Related WP#	WP2 OPERAS construction phase framework development
KER Champion	Yannick Legré
Type	Other Tangible
Target Audience	Internal and external stakeholders

KERI Status Summary

As of the current reporting period, the KERI framework is progressing according to the planned schedule, with key milestones achieved and clear timelines for upcoming tasks.

In 2023, the establishment of the Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) marked a significant milestone in the governance structure. This newly formed board is actively shaping the ERIC governance model and aligning it with ERIC requirements. Continuous development and refinement of governance policies are underway, featuring collaboration with the BGR and various national nodes to achieve a comprehensive and representative governance model.

The financial framework has seen substantial progress with the draft of an initial multiannual financial plan in 2023. This plan outlines the strategies for financial sustainability and funding mechanisms essential for long-term operations. In 2024, efforts are focused on designing the financial framework to comply with relevant ISO standards for quality and risk management, aiming for certification by the end of the year.

The risk management and capacity plan, an integral part of KERI, has finally made headway. Although the submission of the risk management framework was initially due by the end of November 2023, it had been delayed, however it was recently delivered at the end of May 2024. Continuous updates to the risk management plan are being conducted in collaboration with the BGR to ensure comprehensive risk mitigation strategies. This framework will address the varying risks associated with the governance and funding mechanisms of the ERIC.

Simultaneously, the human resource framework is being developed. Between 2023 and 2024, a pan-European employment framework emphasising equal opportunities,

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gender equality, and inclusiveness is being formulated.

Updates to the medium and long-term strategic plans are ongoing. These plans, spanning from 2023 to 2025, will guide OPERAS through the transition to an ERIC and beyond, ensuring alignment with the overarching goals of fostering open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

In conclusion, KERI is on track with its development milestones. The progress made in establishing the governance and financial frameworks, coupled with ongoing efforts in risk management and strategic planning, positions OPERAS well for a successful transition to an ERIC. Regular updates and collaborative efforts with the BGR and national nodes will continue to drive the successful implementation of KERI. The timeline for KERI includes significant milestones such as the finalisation of the ERIC Application Dossier by August 2025, validation of the dossier and Member States' support by June 2024, and preparation for the ERIC application submission. The official application for ERIC status is anticipated in 2026, with the creation of the ERIC expected in 2027.

KERI Communication Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target	# at the end of project	First reporting period	Percentage
Engage internal stakeholders in the process and activities for OPERAS becoming an ERIC	ONGOING	AoC, STB, EA, GA and SAC	5	4	80%
Develop draft statutes in preparation for the ERIC	ONGOING	Statues agreed	1	N/A	0%
Strengthen commitment of existing OPERAS GA members in the new OPERAS ERIC preparation	ONGOING	Countries represented in the BGR	15	10 ¹¹	67%
Onboarding new	ONGOING	Countries	5	3	60%

¹¹ BGR was created in late November 2023

countries in the General Assembly		represented in the GA			
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KERI Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Pillar ¹²	Objective	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Pillar 1: Redesigning ecosystem	(O1) OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open ScholComm communities	% of performed actions defined in the Strategic Implementation Plan in total until 2025	31.3%	OPERAS AISBL
		# of actions performed	52 of 166	OPERAS AISBL

Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
ERIC Statutes and legal documents submitted to the EC for approval	Prepare OPERAS ERIC governance model	Initial OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.1)	DONE	SENSITIVE
		Updated OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.5)	CANCELLED	N/A
		Final OPERAS Governance	M36	

¹² 4 Pillars outlined in the OPERAS Strategic Plan 2023-2025 (internal): Pillar 1: Redesigning ecosystem; Pillar 2: Empowering community; Pillar 3: Supporting bibliodiversity; Pillar 4: Fostering Quality

		framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.8)		
	Prepare legal and financial framework of OPERAS ERIC	Initial OPERAS Legal & Financial framework (D2.2)	DONE	SENSITIVE
		Final OPERAS Legal & Financial framework (D2.9)	M36	
		Submit the draft OPERAS ERIC statutes to the EC (D3.3)	M36	
	Define human resources framework	Initial OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy (D2.3)	DONE	SENSITIVE
		Final OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy (D2.6)	M36	

2.2.2. KER2 – OPERAS Innovation Lab

The OPERAS Innovation Lab¹³ aims to strengthen prototyping and FAIR services for the Social Sciences and Humanities community. Supported by WP4, it puts into practice the recommendations from the ‘Future of Scholarly Communication’ report, prepared in the OPERAS-P project through extensive research into OPERAS user needs. The general objective is to establish the OPERAS Innovation Lab as the knowledge hub for the OPERAS community, providing guidelines and counselling to stakeholders wishing to engage with innovative outputs, and liaising with those stakeholders and relevant e-infrastructure providers. The further objectives are to:

- Structure the Innovation Lab within OPERAS by establishing working relationships with OPERAS members and other e-infrastructure providers, who may offer services for innovative and FAIR outputs.

¹³ <https://lab.operas-eu.org/>

- Provide coherent and up-to-date knowledge on innovations to the OPERAS community.
- Support and sustain innovative outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines.
- Strengthen the prestige of innovative publications through prototyping their evaluation.

KER2 Overview

KER #	KER2
KER Full Name	OPERAS Innovation Lab
KER Description	OPERAS Innovation Lab is a support mechanism for scholarly communication in SSH. Its goal is to assist researchers, companies and scholarly institutions in planning and developing novel and/or improved solutions. The OPERAS Innovation Lab provides support to its stakeholders through innovation observatory, innovation management and innovation research and assessment.
Related WP#	WP4 OPERAS Innovation Lab development
KER Champion	Maciej Maryl, Tomasz Umerle
Type	SCIENTIFIC OR TECH R&D ICT SOFTWARE DIGITAL SOLUTION
Target Audience	Internal and external stakeholders

KER2 Status Summary

The OPERAS Innovation Lab is divided into three elements – innovation observatory, research and support. Until now, the Lab has focused its attention on identifying examples of innovation in SSH publishing, communicating them and providing guidelines based on analysing them. Moving forward, based partly on these experiences, the service offer (support for SSH scholarly communication innovation) will become a key support service for the wider OPERAS community.

The OPERAS Innovation Lab continues building its capacity for innovation competences development, innovation research and support in the area of open scholarly communication in SSH.

The Lab has solidified its internal structure and identified key areas of interest to be: 1) innovation observatory, policies and recommendations 2) research on innovation; 3) innovation support as a tool for OPERAS services development and as a resource for the SSH community to pilot solutions for key problems.

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As of now, the observatory has entered its operational phase with various community engagement and publishing (see the Lab's blog) activities. The research part of the lab has identified important case studies of SSH open scholarly communication and studied them to deliver guidelines. Finally, the innovation support mechanism has been preliminarily tested for initial feedback from the community.

The last year of OPERAS PLUS project will be dedicated to establishing a sustainable workflow for the observatory content creation, delivering final reports on case studies and operationalising the mechanism for the Lab's support mechanism.

For the support mechanism it is planned to prepare calls for engagement from the community in four key areas: problems/challenges identification, ideas/solutions proposals, partnerships building and funding identification. These will be regularly communicated with the OPERAS community and will lead to the announcement of the 1st Open Call for pilots in autumn 2024.

Challenges and Strategic Issues:

A primary challenge facing the Lab is achieving operational proficiency in delivering support for the community: organising inputs of information from them in a way that can lead to fruitful pilot projects that can then be scaled up and successfully deployed.

This requires a flexible and adaptable approach based on experiences of other innovation labs which already have a good track record of functioning in different settings, also academic ones.

Also, access to pilot funding is an issue, especially in the pre-ERIC phase. One idea is to introduce a dedicated budget line item, OPERAS Innovation Fund. However, cannot be immediate until more national contributions are collected, therefore funding requires the use of other mechanisms, such as applying for cascading funding, or relying on internal resources (in-kind) of the Lab's members.

Conclusion:

The Lab is in its key moment of engaging the community to provide tangible value in advancing the open scholarly communication in SSH through piloting activities. In order to achieve this, the Lab needs to develop processes that facilitate community engagement more effectively and efficiently that can lead to new pilot projects that are targeting the community's needs.

KER2 Communication Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target	# at the end of project	First reporting period	Percentage
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# of blog posts on the observatory	M1-36	researchers, companies, academic institutions	30	6	20%
# of presentations	M1-36	researchers, companies, academic institutions	10	4	40%

KER2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Pillar 2: Empowering Community	O9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab	# of calls run through the innovation lab	1	IBL PAN, OPERAS
		# of blog posts on the observatory	9	IBL PAN
		# of new services proposed to the service portfolio	2	IBL PAN, OPERAS
		# of new project proposals submitted	2	IBL PAN, OPERAS
		# of case studies	2	IBL PAN

Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
The Innovation Lab is defined	Set up internal research seminar	Seminar held	IN PROGRESS	
	Prepare the Innovation Lab Terms of Reference (ToR)	ToR presented to STB	IN PROGRESS	
WP4 outputs have been delivered	Guidelines on publishing and evaluating innovative outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities	D4.1 submitted (M27)	IN PROGRESS	
	Organise community validation workshop	MS7 (M16)	ACHIEVED	OPERAS Conf'24

				Workshop 2 ¹⁴
	Develop evaluation framework for innovative outputs (T4.3)	Documented procedure	PLANNED FOR END SEPT 2024	
An OPERAS Innovation fund is set-up	Define the scope and the budget envelope of the innovation fund	Included in end of year budget	IN PROGRESS	
	Communicate about the Innovation Fund	TBD	PLANNED FOR 2025	
	Launch call(s) for participation	TBD	PLANNED FOR 2025	

2.2.3. KER3 – OPERAS portfolio of services

The OPERAS portfolio of services aims at structuring and developing the OPERAS services in the specific context of OPERAS being a distributed infrastructure. Designed during the OPERAS-D (Design) project¹⁵ (Jan 2017 – Jun 2018), initiated in the course of the OPERAS-P (Prepare) project¹⁶ (Jul 2019 – Jun 2021), OPERAS catalogue of service needs further work to gain consistency and start operating, according to the principle “as FAIR as possible”. The specific objectives are to:

- Establish the legal, organisational, contractual framework needed to obtain a working catalogue of services.
- Integrate more OPERAS services into the EOSC and related catalogues of services (SSHOC, OpenAIRE)
- Give dedicated support for the development of current services identified in the OPERAS-D and OPERAS-P design study
- Leverage on the FAIRification tools and process as suggested by the community in WP3 and WP4
- Achieve design studies to prepare the development of future services

KER3 Overview

KER #	KER3
KER Full Name	OPERAS portfolio of services

¹⁴

<https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/programme/day-1-conference-programme/conference-workshops-details/#workshop-2>

¹⁵ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/past-projects/operas-d/>

¹⁶ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/past-projects/operas-p/>

KER Description	OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research. There are three types of services provided by OPERAS: Managed, Community and Internal. These services can be grouped into seven categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Training, and Operational and Collaboration Tools.
Related WP#	WP5 Technical support to OPERAS services
KER Champion	Sy Holsinger
Type	SERVICES
Target Audience	SSH Researchers; Authors; Editors, Editorial Managers; Publishers; Libraries; Translators

KER3 Status Summary

The OPERAS Plus portfolio of services continues to show significant progress, reinforcing OPERAS' role as a pivotal infrastructure in the open scholarly communication landscape for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). The portfolio has successfully advanced its service integration, currently managing a comprehensive suite designed to support European researchers, addressing their identified needs in the SSH domain. As detailed in the project documents, the portfolio encompasses a range of services structured into categories including Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Training, Operational, and Collaboration Tools. These services collectively aim to enhance the accessibility and openness of scholarly communication.

As of now, OPERAS has successfully moved several services from development phases into production. The shift towards marketing and sustainability marks a new phase where the focus is on enhancing the visibility and usage of these services. The introduction of community-centric features and the incorporation of feedback mechanisms exemplify a proactive approach to user engagement.

Currently (Status April 2024), OPERAS has 6 services in the OPERAS service catalogue¹⁷ and 11 in OPERAS service portfolio¹⁸. GoTriple, a discovery platform for SSH publications in multiple languages, now provides access to over 15 million documents from more

¹⁷ Customer-facing list of all live services offered along with relevant information about these services (FitSM-0 V3)

¹⁸ Internal list that details all the services offered by a service provider, including those in preparation, live and discontinued (FitSM-0 V3)

than 1,300 data sources. Hypotheses¹⁹, a dedicated service within the portfolio fostering research dialogues and impact through academic blogging, draws approximately 1.1 million visits per month, hosts around 5,000 active blogs, and engages over 20,000 active accounts. VERA²⁰, activating participatory research in Citizen Science, supports around 100 projects. PRISM, a tool for increasing transparency about peer review processes for monographs, hosts approximately 6000 titles and connects 18 publishers. Pathfinder²¹, a service aimed at finding editorial services for academic publishing, collaborates with 4 service providers to offer 27 options. Metrics²², a service measuring usage and impact of Open Access content, engages with 49 publishers and about 3,300 books tracked, complemented by the installation of around 40 widgets to enhance user interaction and accessibility. Mondaecus²³, a platform to support collaborative translations that brings together translators, proofreaders, and subject matter experts to work on high-quality translations, is in the pilot phase, contributing and stimulating the multilingual approach so important for the SSH domain. The Innovation Lab fosters the development of new services, engaging researchers in the co-creation of innovative solutions. Significant progress includes the operationalisation of the OPERAS ID, which simplifies user access across all OPERAS services and currently integrates Google, ORCID and EGI Check-in, others in the development pipeline, and the FitSM training that enhances service management capabilities within the community. These developments underscore OPERAS' commitment to fostering an integrated and efficient research infrastructure.

Challenges and Strategic Considerations

A primary challenge facing OPERAS Plus is achieving financial sustainability. This is crucial as OPERAS moves towards establishing itself as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) by 2028. The project is actively exploring sustainable funding models to support long-term operations, which remains a key focus area.

Moreover, increasing user engagement and the utilisation of services are critical. Despite substantial advancements in service development, transitioning from a project-focused to a market-driven approach in outreach and user adoption has been identified as an area requiring significant effort and strategic focus.

Growth Opportunities and Future Directions

OPERAS Plus is strategically expanding its services to include new initiatives like the translation service and the development of the OPERAS Innovation Lab, which aims to foster innovation within the SSH community. The Innovation Lab, in particular, is set to launch pilot campaigns that will test and refine services in alignment with community

¹⁹ <https://en.hypotheses.org/>

²⁰ <https://vera.operas-eu.org/>

²¹ <https://pathfinder.operas-eu.org/>

²² <https://metrics.operas-eu.org/>

²³ <https://mondaecus.com/>

needs and feedback.

The integration with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and efforts to align with its standards will enhance OPERAS' visibility and integration within the broader European research infrastructure. This alignment is expected to facilitate greater interoperability and collaboration across research communities.

Conclusion:

The OPERAS Plus portfolio is at a pivotal stage, where it is transitioning core services into sustainable operations while expanding its scope through innovative projects. By addressing financial sustainability challenges, enhancing marketing strategies, and fostering user engagement, OPERAS Plus aims to solidify its foundation and extend its impact within the scholarly communication sector.

KER3 Communication Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target	# at the end of project	First reporting period	Percentage
Showcase services for SSH researchers	2024-25	SSH researchers	TBC	N/A	N/A
Disseminate the provision of services	2024-25	Publishers, Libraries, Research Performing Organisations, Infrastructure service providers	TBC	N/A	N/A
Provide support for OA publishing	2024-25	Publishers	TBC	N/A	N/A

KER3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Pillar 2: Empowering community Pillar 4: Fostering Quality	Services	# of services in a catalogue	6	OPERAS AISBL
		# of services in a portfolio	11	
	Business models for Services	# of services with a clearly defined business model	IN PROGRESS	

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	FitSM	# of FitSM training courses held	4	
		# of personal FitSM certifications	45	

Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
OPERAS Integrated Management System initial version operational	Create initial structure	N/A	DONE	https://operas.atlassian.net/wiki/home
	Provide access to relevant members	Instructions circulated to relevant mailing lists	DONE	158 ACTIVE USERS
	Populate with initial content	D5.1 (M12)	DONE	https://operas.atlassian.net/wiki/home
Service strategy and roadmap published	Publish an annual service strategy and roadmap	Draft version available for STB in Sept 2024	IN PROGRESS	
Business models for all current and new services (incl. licensing models) established	Service Design and Transition Packages (SDTP) available for all services	D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5 (M12)	DONE	https://operas.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/OPERAS/pages/884870/Service+Design+and+Transition+Packages+SDTP
Service reviews, including capacity requirements (e.g. sustainability) conducted	Prepare service review template	Q3 2024	TO BE STARTED	
	Conduct service review	Q4 2024	TO BE STARTED	
FitSM organisation certification achieved and retained	Conduct initial IMS Maturity Assessment	Q4 2024	FUTURE ACTION	
	Conduct internal audit of OPERAS Integrated	Q2 2025	FUTURE ACTION	

	management system			
	Conduct certification audit against FitSM	Q1 2026	FUTURE ACTION	

2.2.4. KER4 – OPERAS user training framework

The overall objective of this KER is to establish a comprehensive framework for developing effective open science and scholarly communication training tailored to the needs of OPERAS services users and other stakeholders. This KER will act as a central hub, collecting and maintaining a registry of strategies and methods used in the creation of existing training materials and those proposed for future development, with a strong focus on the research and communication life cycle in SSH.

This KER will integrate internal training activities offered by OPERAS and raise awareness of external training initiatives and materials, thereby enhancing the overall training ecosystem. A crucial element of this framework is the collection and organisation of existing training resources and sessions for OPERAS services such as GoTriple, VERA, PRISM, Pathfinder, and internal training and certification programs like FitSM. Additionally, the framework leverages training activities from past and current projects like Skills4EOSC, DIAMAS, etc., maintaining close relationships with the OPERAS community and national nodes to consolidate and disseminate training-related information.

Emphasising the importance of national nodes, the framework supports these nodes in maintaining and harnessing multiculturalism and multilingualism, which are core values of OPERAS. This is particularly vital for ensuring that training activities reflect the diverse linguistic and cultural landscape of the OPERAS community.

This KER also includes a methodological approach that has been rigorously developed, tested, and applied to continuously evaluate user engagement with OPERAS services ([UCO-FRAME](#)). By understanding users' goals, tasks, resources, and environments, and applying state-of-the-art usability and user experience principles, the framework ensures the user-centeredness and sustainability of current and future research infrastructure (RI) services.

By addressing these elements, KER4 aims to create a robust and sustainable training environment within OPERAS, enhancing the usability, accessibility, and impact of OPERAS services.

KER4 Overview

KER #	KER4
KER Full Name	OPERAS user training framework
KER Description	The overall objective of this KER is to establish a comprehensive framework for developing effective open science and scholarly communication training tailored to the needs of OPERAS services users and other stakeholders. This KER will act as a central hub, collecting and maintaining a registry of strategies and methods used in the creation of existing training materials and those proposed for future development, with a strong focus on the research and communication life cycle in SSH. All tasks will take into account issues of multiculturalism, multilingualism and FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse).
Related WP#	WP6 User engagement and training
KER Champion	Franjo Pehar
Type	SERVICES
Target Audience	Academia/Universities; Research and Technology Organisations: EU and Member State Policymakers

KER4 Status Summary

The OPERAS training framework caters to two primary audiences: users and providers of OPERAS services, and the broader scholarly communication community, including stakeholders from the SSH domains. Rooted in the OPERAS Training Strategy — an internal document — it identifies opportunities for training facilitation, delineating areas, activities, targeted user groups, and training providers. Through OPERAS PLUS initiatives, the framework aims to streamline service delivery and foster acceptance of existing and future services. Its primary goals include leveraging a common framework for user-centred quality objectives and offering training on OPERAS services. Additionally, the framework serves as a tool to align efforts within the OPERAS community, promoting a shared understanding of OPERAS' goals regarding Open Science practices and FAIR principles. It consolidates methodologies, tools, and guidelines from various projects and collaborations to support the scholarly communication community in the SSH fields.

The development of the OPERAS training framework began in April 2024 and will continue until Month 36 of the OPERAS Plus project. This timeline indicates that the framework will be established after the reporting period of the "Plan for Exploitation

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and Dissemination of Results." In the meantime, some activities have already started, and some are already complete.

For instance, a crucial task related to service and user identification has been completed (WP6, Task 6.1; M1-M6). This task has precisely identified and categorised existing services and their respective users. This foundational step ensures that each service can be tailored to its target audience, which is also relevant for developing the training framework. It ensures that the framework evolves with the addition of new services and training needs.

As part of WP6, a methodological framework for continuous evaluation of user engagement with OPERAS services is being developed (Task 6.2; M3-M36). Designed with rigour, the so-called UCQ-FRAME's primary aim is to infuse user-centred principles across all OPERAS projects, ensuring that user needs are always prioritised. Starting in Month 18 (Task 6.3, M18-M30), the UCQ-FRAME will be implemented and tested across a number of OPERAS services such as GoTriple, VERA, and Pathfinder. Based on the feedback, the framework will be continuously updated and implemented as a comprehensive guide made available via Confluence. The objective is to equip the entire OPERAS community and project teams with the essential knowledge and tools needed to champion user-centred design (UCD) principles in the realm of open scholarly communication services.

The experience and insights gained during the development and implementation phases of the UCQ-FRAME will serve as invaluable resources for shaping the training framework. Lessons learned, best practices identified, and challenges encountered throughout the UCQ-FRAME process will inform the design, structure, and methodologies employed in the training framework.

Challenges and Strategic Considerations

The development of the OPERAS training framework faces some challenges and strategic considerations. A primary challenge involves collecting and maintaining a comprehensive registry. This registry encompasses strategies and methods for developing training materials, as well as gathering data on existing training activities, resources, and materials for open scholarly communication and publishing.

Another important aspect is ensuring the usability, accessibility, and sustainability of training resources and activities. Additionally, aligning public communication and marketing efforts with the diverse needs of the OPERAS community poses a significant challenge. Moreover, maintaining close relationships with national nodes and upholding multiculturalism and multilingualism as core values necessitate strategic coordination and support.

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Furthermore, ensuring the seamless evolution of the framework to accommodate new services and training needs presents a significant challenge. The dynamic nature of the OPERAS ecosystem demands continuous adaptation and refinement to meet emerging services and evolving user requirements.

Growth Opportunities and Future Directions

Despite the challenges, the OPERAS training framework offers several growth opportunities and avenues for future development. Leveraging insights from past and ongoing projects, the framework can extend its influence within the open scholarly communication community. Furthermore, its focus on providing specialised training for core OPERAS services lays a solid groundwork for enhancing user engagement and proficiency. Moving forward, the framework's phased development and implementation approach ensure flexibility and adaptability to cater to the evolving needs of the OPERAS community.

Conclusion:

In summary, the OPERAS training framework marks a crucial step in establishing a resilient and enduring training ecosystem within OPERAS. By tackling challenges, leveraging growth opportunities, and cultivating strategic collaborations, KER4 endeavours to augment the usability, accessibility, and impact of OPERAS services. This initiative aligns with OPERAS' overarching ambition of attaining European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) status by 2028, reaffirming its dedication to amplifying user engagement within the scholarly communication community.

KER4 Communication Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target	# at the end of project	First reporting period	Percentage
# of presentations, workshops, or events organised to disseminate and raise awareness about the UCQ-FRAME	Yearly	10 events	TBD	3 events	30%
# of views and downloads of the UCQ-FRAME	Yearly	300 views 150	TBD	130 views	43% 61%

document from the Zenodo platform.		downloads		92 downloads	
# of presentations, workshops, or events organised to disseminate and raise awareness about the OPERAS training framework	Yearly	5	TBD	0	0% (TO BE STARTED)
# of training resources related to OPERAS services (videos, tutorials, presentations, guides, etc.) detected, collected and included in the OPERAS training registry	Quarterly/ Yearly	30	TBD	0	0% (TO BE STARTED)
# of training sessions/workshops/webinars conducted on open science, scholarly communication, UX/UCD methodologies etc.	Quarterly/ Yearly	10	TBD	0	0% (TO BE STARTED)
# of participants attending FitSM training sessions organised by OPERAS	Quarterly/ Yearly	75	TBD	45	60%
# of papers, articles, reports, blog posts etc. published on topics related to user engagement and training in scholarly	Yearly	5	TBD	0	0%

communication, open science, and OPERAS related topics.					
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KER4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data	Responsible to provide
Pillar 4: Fostering Quality	O4. Clear set of well-defined and operational services (portfolio of services + fostering quality)	# UX maturity level increase	% increase in UX maturity levels post-UCQ-FRAME implementation will be monitored after the conclusion of the OPERAS Plus project.	UNIZD
		#UCQ-FRAME adoption rate	# of times the UCQ-FRAME is being implemented across different projects or services (formative / summative)	UNIZD
		#UCQ-FRAME evolution index	Measures the frequency and extent of updates to the UCQ-FRAME, reflecting its adaptability to new UX methods and findings from implementation case studies. The index will track the following categories: a) Methodology Updates, b) Methods and Tools Integration, c) Case Study and Experimentation Feedback, d) UCD/UX	

			Best Practices and Standards Alignment, e) Community and Stakeholder Contributions	
		#UX research publication count	# of research outputs (papers, articles, or presentations) that focus on the findings or insights gained from applying the UCQ-FRAME in various contexts	UNIZD/All
Pillar 2: Empowering community	O5: OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices (training + empowering of the community)	# of training participants	# of training sessions and participants	Training coordinators, OPERAS member organisations, Project coordinators
Pillar 4: Fostering Quality	O6: OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery	# of UCD/UX training sessions	# of training sessions conducted on UCD/UX methodologies	UNIZD
		# of training participants	# of participants in training sessions on UCD/UX methodologies	UNIZD
		# of professionals	Total # of individuals associated with the	

		certified for usability and user experience	OPERAS initiative who have obtained any kind of usability and user experience certification.	
		# of FitSM training courses held	4	
		# of personal FitSM certifications	45	

Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
Developed OPERAS Training strategy	Identification of relevant training areas	D6.3 (M36)	DONE	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1L4Sn5Ru3zhhQD9MyIDoeecYZrD0p3rgZDbL9oSTYjw/edit#slide=id.g2cd97972bba_0_260
	Identification of relevant targeted user groups	D6.3 (M36)	DONE	
	Identification of opportunities for facilitating and performing training	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS	
	Identification of training providers	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS	
	Description of training activities	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS	
Designed Competence	Preparation of Open Science,	SKILLS4EOSC D5.2	DUE AUG 2025	

Center for Social Sciences and Humanities	FAIR and RDM learning path for SSH			
	Recommendation of actions for the set-up of Open Science and RDM thematic trainings	SKILLS4EOSC D5.6	DUE 2025	AUG
Integrated dissemination of Knowledge into OPERAS Communication	Common framework defining the methodology for achieving user-centred quality objectives (D6.1)	D6.1 (M10)	DONE	https://zenodo.org/records/8081977
	Report on implementation of the methodological framework for user-centred quality on selected services	MS6 (M14)	DONE	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1adDEIMVl_bLqjNTmoDLLKwzx6JqUcxSZe/view
		D6.2 (M30)	IN PROGRESS	
	Framework for the development of open science and scholarly communication training	D6.3 (M36)	IN PROGRESS	
Knowledge acquired in IT Service Management using FitSM (lightweight ITSM standard) as the reference framework	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	FitSM included in published version	IN PROGRESS	
	Identify (new) opportunities for organising training courses	CONTINUOUS	IN PROGRESS	i.e https://operas-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/FitSM-FND_

				Overview-Agenda_23Apr2024_OPERAS-Conf24.docx.pdf
	Organise courses	1 per year (min)	IN PROGRESS	
Knowledge acquired on the individual services offered by OPERAS	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	Incl. in OPERAS Training Strategy	DONE	Internal doc
	Conduct webinars and/or hands-on trainings	1 per service per year	IN PROGRESS	e.g. PRISM ²⁴ , VERA ²⁵
OPERAS services alignment with EOSC and FAIR requirements webinar or presentation	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	Incl. in OPERAS Training Strategy	IN PROGRESS	
	Conduct webinars or presentation	1 workshop for the service providers held	PLANNED FOR 2025	
OPERAS Integrated Management System for Federation Members webinar and/or presentation	Ensure inclusion in the training strategy	Incl. in OPERAS Training Strategy	DONE	Internal doc
	Conduct webinars or presentation	Webinar held	PLANNED FOR 2025	

2.2.5. KER5 – OPERAS national nodes

This KER deals with the implementation of OPERAS national nodes and the framing of their connection with the central hub. National nodes play a pivotal role in establishing

²⁴ <https://youtu.be/XMnsZqWcKGA?si=KN6pQOhGgLSjGvnl>

²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9hXxmDpd5kM>

a connection point to outside the OPERAS community, in promoting a proximity relation with local communities, helping to identify needs, provide services, and training. They are in a decisive position to find a balanced solution for the keeping of national languages as fully scientific valid modes of expression, while promoting them on the international level. This strategy is fully aligned with the paths to outreach in the European Research Area (ERA), and with the development and implementation of the OPERAS catalogue of services at the local level.

KER5 Overview

KER #	KER5
KER Full Name	OPERAS national nodes
KER Description	National nodes play a pivotal role in establishing a connection point to outside the OPERAS community, in promoting a proximity relation with local communities, helping to identify needs, provide services, and training. They are in a decisive position to find a balanced solution for the keeping of national languages as fully scientific valid modes of expression, while promoting them on the international level.
Related WP#	WP7 Support to national nodes
KER Champion	Delfim Leão
Type	OTHER INTANGIBLE
Target Audience	OPERAS Members; Special Interest Groups (SIGs) members; national communities (researchers, publishers, librarians, etc); OPERAS services target users; research policy-makers and funding organisations; European Research Infrastructures

KER5 Status Summary

The development of the OPERAS national nodes received a great boost during 2023, with the creation of the first roadmap for all the existing and future nodes of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure. Within the work carried out during the year, guidelines were established for the existence and sustainability of the nodes, which represent OPERAS at the national and local levels and understand the needs of each national community.

The nodes active on the OPERAS-PLUS project established a vision for the OPERAS nodes, together with a strategy to be followed during the coming years. The strategy organises requirements and metrics to be collected and supported in each national

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community.

The OPERAS-PLUS Work Package 7, which is dedicated to supporting the national nodes, has also put together efforts to deliver a second report on the OPERAS national nodes challenges and opportunities – a work that was successfully completed in February 2024.

OPERAS currently has 13 national representatives. The basic information of the nodes, together with representative institutions and persons, can be found on the OPERAS website²⁶.

KER5 Communication Activities

Description	Timeframe	Target ²⁷	# at the end of project	First reporting period	Percentage
Visitors on OPERAS website	2023	26,000	TBD	27,811	+100%
Followers on social media	2023	4,000	TBD	4,533 (1,064 new in 2023)	+100%
Social media posts	2023	500	TBD	587 posts across all networks (X, LinkedIn, FB, Instagram)	+100%
Blog posts	2023	20	TBD	23	+100%

KER5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Pillar	Objective	Indicator	Data
Pillar 1: Redesigning ecosystem	O1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of	New members (per country, European and non-European, ordinary)	4 (University of Lorraine, University of Rennes, Library University of Cyprus, CSIC)
		New national	3 new core member

²⁶ Available at: <https://operas-eu.org/operas-national-nodes/>.

²⁷ Targets to be updated as 100% has already been achieved

	the SSH Open scholarly	nodes/new member countries	countries Spain, Norway, Finland (FECYT, ERIH+, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies)
		Days of engagement events	17 hours of self-organised events from the OPERAS national nodes

Activity Plan (See D8.3)

Key Result	Related Actions	Milestone	Status	Link to evidence
Established OPERAS national nodes for each member of the EA	Sharing good practices	Internal WP Kick-off meeting with prospective national nodes (MS2)	DONE	Internal agenda
	National node can be used as regional node when needed and no linguistic barriers exist	Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes (D7.1)	DONE	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10725785
		Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes (D7.2)	DONE	https://zenodo.org/records/8289238
		Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes – Final (D7.3)	DUE MAY 2025	
	Formalising and securing relations between OPERAS hub and the nodes	Final OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.8)	DUE MAY 2025	
	Aligning Hub and national node governance	Final OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.8)	DUE AUG 2025	

3. OPERAS Key Performance Indicators - Update

The table below briefly provides an update on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of the communication and dissemination measures. They are adapted to the developments in the communication channels and the evolving needs of the project as well as the services.

Channel / Engagement	Activity	Inform/engage	Target Groups	Key Performance Indicators (KPI)	Measure defined in beginning	Update
OPERAS website	Main access point for RI and project results, links to other engagements with an event calendar for the community	Inform	All stakeholders defined before	# unique visitors	> 800/month	> 1100/month
OPERAS blog	News, community posts, different series, i.e. from the Special Interest Groups	Engage	All stakeholders	# of posts in total # unique visitors	> 15/year > 2.500/month	> 20/year > 3000/month
Newsletter	News	Inform	All stakeholders, but especially for OPERAS members	# of newsletters # of new subscribers # of total subscribers	> 3 times/year > 50 new/year > 500 subscribers	> 3 times/year > 50 new/year > 600 subscribers
Social media	Regular posting of relevant news	Inform	Community, all stakeholders	# tweets (incl. retweets) # twitter followers	>300/year > 30 new followers/month	>300/year > 30 new followers/month

Channel / Engagement	Activity	Inform/engage	Target Groups	Key Performance Indicators (KPI)	Measure defined in beginning	Update
The road to FAIR blog	Regular posts on FAIR topics	Engage	Community	# of posts # of authors	> 20/year > 5	Not related to the project anymore
Events	International conference face-to-face	Engage	Community	# participants	> 120	>120
	Assembly of the Commons		OPERAS members	# assemblies # participants	3 < 50	3 < 50
	General Assembly		National ministries, supporting member	# assemblies # participants	6 < 120	6 < 120
	Virtual workshops		Community, researchers, service provider, librarians, publishers, policymakers	#workshops internal and external # participants	< 50	< 50
Campaigns	Planned communication campaign on several channels	Inform	Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Librarians, Publishers	# campaigns	3	4
Policy briefs	Short papers on different topics	Inform	National ministries, Social Sciences and Humanities research policymakers	# briefs	< 5	<3

In the development of the project, KPIs are adopted and updated upon further evaluation. As the OPERAS Research Infrastructure is growing, the awareness of the RI is growing. Therefore, the reachable number of readers/viewers/engaged stakeholders can be raised as indicated in the update column.

The “Road to FAIR”-Blog KPI (#20 blog posts) turned out to be not a useful KPI. Created in the context of another project, the blog “Road to FAIR” was meant for communication among community members involved in distinct FAIR-related projects with their own communication tools and objectives. Therefore, it does not justify continuing to provide active support to the blog “Road to FAIR” in the OPERAS-PLUS project.

Finally, as the metrics for the services are defined, we can add the following KPIs for the main services. These are collected on a monthly basis via the STB and will be reported on in the final version of the report at M30.

Services	GoTriple	Metrics	PRISM	Hypotheses
Metrics to count	# user profiles created # documents # projects # authors # languages supported # data sources # unique visitors (monthly)	# publishers on the platform # books being tracked # metrics per book # widgets installed	# publishers with at least 1 record # titles/works with a PRISM record	# active blogs # unique visitors # active accounts
Services	VERA	Pathfinder	OPERAS ID	FitSM Training
Metrics to count	# total projects # total profiles created # visitors	# services listed # registered users # service providers # visitors # searches	# registered users # services integrated with # identity providers integrated	# courses # participants # certifications

Services	Innovation lab
Metrics to count	#Number of pilots run through the innovation lab #Number of blog posts on the observatory #Number of innovative outputs (Boost to economic developments/ new markets/ consequences of research) #Increase of Technology Readiness Levels (TBD) #new services added to the catalogue

4. Conclusion

The OPERAS-PLUS project has made significant strides towards establishing OPERAS as a sustainable and robust research infrastructure for open scholarly communication within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). This updated Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) captures the progress made and outlines a strategic roadmap for future efforts.

One of the key achievements of the project has been the development of comprehensive frameworks across various domains including governance, financial sustainability, and technical management. The project has successfully identified and articulated the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that will serve as the cornerstone for future exploitation activities. These KERs include the OPERAS core governance finance and management framework, the Innovation Lab, the portfolio of services, the user training framework and the establishment of national nodes. Each of these KERs is underpinned by a tailored strategy that addresses the unique needs and challenges of their respective stakeholders.

As the project progresses towards its final stages, the focus will shift towards refining these frameworks and ensuring their seamless implementation. Continuous engagement with the wider SSH community, along with a commitment to innovation and quality, will be crucial for the successful exploitation of project results. Future steps include the finalisation of work to complete the detailed plans for each KER, ensuring they are fully developed and ready for exploitation. The OPERAS-PLUS PEDR combines specific key results with tailored dissemination strategies to ensure the successful uptake of project outcomes. This approach not only highlights the project's achievements, but also sets a clear path for future developments and the continued

support. By focusing on the sustainability and scalability of its services and infrastructure, OPERAS-PLUS is establishing a foundation that will enable continued growth and adaptation in the landscape of SSH.

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Annex

Horizon Results Platform

The following tables use the information directly requested in the Horizon Results Platform as template for each KER. The tables provided below have been taken from individual pages on the OPERAS-PLUS Confluence space where content is being collated. These are draft versions with the currently available information. All information will be collected and presented in the final version of this report at M30.

KER1 - OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	Cascading OPERAS core governance, finance, and management framework for building a sustainable research infrastructure in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to the national nodes
*Message / Teaser to potential user	Not applicable
*Video/Image	Not applicable
*Result type	Select only 1
	<input type="checkbox"/> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.).
	<input type="checkbox"/> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the

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	<p>prototype and commercial readiness.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify in the Result Description.</p>								
*EU Missions	<p>Select any that apply</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Adaptation to climate change</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Cancer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Climate-neutral and smart cities</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Oceans, seas, and waters</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Soil health and food</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable</p>								
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing to from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Target audiences (up to 3)</th> <th>Our Needs (any that apply)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions</td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)	<input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy	<input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy	<input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions	<input type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended
Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)								
<input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy								
<input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy								
<input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions	<input type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended								

	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential	financing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations <input type="checkbox"/> Incubators / Accelerators <input type="checkbox"/> Marketing Mentoring or Coaching <input type="checkbox"/> Financing Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Technology Transfer Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Legal / IPR advise <input type="checkbox"/> I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party <input type="checkbox"/> Investor readiness training <input type="checkbox"/> Investor introductions <input type="checkbox"/> Business plan development <input type="checkbox"/> Expanding to more markets /finding new customers <input type="checkbox"/> Executive Training <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
	<input type="checkbox"/> Research and Technology Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Academia/Universities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Private Investors	<input type="checkbox"/> Business Angels

		<input type="checkbox"/> Venture Capital <input type="checkbox"/> Crowd-funding Equity <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)		

About us

Other related projects	
*Result Contributors	OPERAS members; National communities
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description: OPERAS website
	Link: https://operas-eu.org/
	(add others)

Result Description and Influence

*Result description (1200 characters max)	All national nodes use our templates	
*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)	Please select up to three	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and rural development <input type="checkbox"/> Banking and financial services <input type="checkbox"/> Better Regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Borders and security <input type="checkbox"/> Budget <input type="checkbox"/> Business and industry	<input type="checkbox"/> Foreign affairs and security policy <input type="checkbox"/> Fraud prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Home affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Humanitarian aid and civil protection <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional affairs <input type="checkbox"/> International Partnerships

	<input type="checkbox"/> Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Competition <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input type="checkbox"/> Culture and media <input type="checkbox"/> Customs <input type="checkbox"/> Defence <input type="checkbox"/> Digital economy and society <input type="checkbox"/> Economy, finance and the euro <input type="checkbox"/> Education and training <input type="checkbox"/> Employment and social affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> EU enlargement <input type="checkbox"/> European neighbourhood policy <input type="checkbox"/> Food safety	<input type="checkbox"/> Justice and fundamental rights <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime affairs and fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> Migration and asylum <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Public health <input type="checkbox"/> Regional policy <input type="checkbox"/> Research and innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Single market <input type="checkbox"/> Space <input type="checkbox"/> Sport <input type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation <input type="checkbox"/> Trade <input type="checkbox"/> Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Youth
*Tags / Keywords		
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 1: No poverty <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 2: Zero hunger <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 4: Quality education <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 5: Gender equality <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 10: Reducing inequalities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 13: Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 14: Life below water	

	<input type="checkbox"/> Goal 15: Life on land <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	Please select one <input type="checkbox"/> 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) <input type="checkbox"/> 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) <input type="checkbox"/> 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) <input type="checkbox"/> 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - Market Deployment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	Not applicable
Do you already have customers for this result?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	
Do you have a scalable business model?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.

Investors Corner

*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?	Please select one
	<input type="checkbox"/> <100K <input type="checkbox"/> 101-500K <input type="checkbox"/> 501K-1M <input type="checkbox"/> 1M-2.5M <input type="checkbox"/> 2.6M-5M <input type="checkbox"/> 5.1M-10M <input type="checkbox"/> >10M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No investment sought
I can provide the following upon request by an interested party	Select any that apply
	<input type="checkbox"/> Short presentation(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Case study(ies)

	<input type="checkbox"/> Related Technology white paper <input type="checkbox"/> A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) <input type="checkbox"/> A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers <input type="checkbox"/> Complete and detailed business plan <input type="checkbox"/> Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? <input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Competitive Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") <input type="checkbox"/> List of investors
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KER2 - OPERAS Innovation Lab

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	OPERAS Innovation Lab: Supporting Great Ideas for Open Communication in SSH
*Message / Teaser to potential user	OPERAS Innovation Lab is a support mechanism for scholarly communication in SSH. Its goal is to assist researchers, companies and scholarly institutions in planning and developing novel and/or improved solutions. OPERAS Innovation Lab provides support to its stakeholders through innovation observatory, innovation management and innovation research and assessment.
*Video/Image	(tbd)
*Result type	Select only 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.).

	<input type="checkbox"/> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.	
	<input type="checkbox"/> ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.)	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.).	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify in the Result Description.	
*EU Missions	Select any that apply	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Adaptation to climate change <input type="checkbox"/> Cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Climate-neutral and smart cities <input type="checkbox"/> Oceans, seas, and waters <input type="checkbox"/> Soil health and food <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p>	
	Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)
	<input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness

	Policy-makers	and possibly influence policy
	<input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended financing
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential	<input type="checkbox"/> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations <input type="checkbox"/> Incubators / Accelerators <input type="checkbox"/> Marketing Mentoring or Coaching <input type="checkbox"/> Financing Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Technology Transfer Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Legal / IPR advise <input type="checkbox"/> I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party <input type="checkbox"/> Investor readiness training <input type="checkbox"/> Investor introductions <input type="checkbox"/> Business plan development <input type="checkbox"/> Expanding to more markets /finding new customers <input type="checkbox"/> Executive Training <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
	<input type="checkbox"/> Research and Technology Organisations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise

		<input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Academia/Universities	<input type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Private Investors	<input type="checkbox"/> Business Angels <input type="checkbox"/> Venture Capital <input type="checkbox"/> Crowd-funding Equity <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)	We are looking for innovators in the SSH field who either want to showcase their work through the OPERAS channels or who seek help in developing their ideas, concepts or services through collaboration with the Lab's network. Additionally, we are looking for researchers, experts performing research on innovation to help us better understand innovation mechanism and the role of innovation evaluation.	

About us

Other related projects	
*Result Contributors	OPERAS AISBL IBL PAN OAPEN UNIZD UNITO CNRS DARIAH
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS AISBL
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:

Find us on	Description:
	Link:
	(add others)

Result Description and Influence

*Result description (1200 characters max)	OPERAS Innovation Lab will be an OPERAS service which deals with innovation observation, management and research. Embedded in the OPERAS organisation, it is being designed as a mechanism which allows a diverse SSH community of researchers, institutions and companies to collaborate and build networks which lead to development of successful, sustainable and exploitable SSH innovations.	
*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)	Please select up to three	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and rural development <input type="checkbox"/> Banking and financial services <input type="checkbox"/> Better Regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Borders and security <input type="checkbox"/> Budget <input type="checkbox"/> Business and industry <input type="checkbox"/> Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Competition <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Culture and media <input type="checkbox"/> Customs <input type="checkbox"/> Defence <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Digital economy and society <input type="checkbox"/> Economy, finance and the euro <input type="checkbox"/> Education and training <input type="checkbox"/> Employment and social affairs	<input type="checkbox"/> Foreign affairs and security policy <input type="checkbox"/> Fraud prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Home affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Humanitarian aid and civil protection <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional affairs <input type="checkbox"/> International Partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Justice and fundamental rights <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime affairs and fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> Migration and asylum <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Public health <input type="checkbox"/> Regional policy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research and innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Single market <input type="checkbox"/> Space

	<input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> EU enlargement <input type="checkbox"/> European neighbourhood policy <input type="checkbox"/> Food safety	<input type="checkbox"/> Sport <input type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation <input type="checkbox"/> Trade <input type="checkbox"/> Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Youth
*Tags / Keywords	innovation Innovation science management ideas management pilot acceleration R&D	
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 1: No poverty <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 2: Zero hunger <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 4: Quality education <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 5: Gender equality <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 10: Reducing inequalities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 13: Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 14: Life below water <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 15: Life on land <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	

Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) <input type="checkbox"/> 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) <input type="checkbox"/> 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - Market Deployment <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	OPERAS Innovation Lab is in the process of working on a selected number of case studies (5 innovations from the SSH community) which will allow it to iteratively shape and test its processes designed to observe, support and evaluate SSH innovation.
Do you already have customers for this result?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	OPERAS Innovation lab aims to provide a professionalised mechanism for the SSH community to engage with the OPERAS ESFRI as a key innovation actor in the SSH. It will offer support in innovation management and provide access to innovation ecosystem of OPERAS consisting of a rich service catalogue and a network of researchers, institutions and companies.
Do you have a scalable business model?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters)	now or at the end of the project?

max)	
Is your result replicable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	now or at the end of the project?
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	now or at the end of the project?
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.
	Europe South America

Investors Corner

*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?	Please select one
	<input type="checkbox"/> <100K <input type="checkbox"/> 101-500K <input type="checkbox"/> 501K-1M <input type="checkbox"/> 1M-2.5M <input type="checkbox"/> 2.6M-5M <input type="checkbox"/> 5.1M-10M <input type="checkbox"/> >10M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No investment sought
I can provide the following upon request by an interested party	Select any that apply
	<input type="checkbox"/> Short presentation(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Case study(ies) <input type="checkbox"/> Related Technology white paper

	<input type="checkbox"/> A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) <input type="checkbox"/> A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers <input type="checkbox"/> Complete and detailed business plan <input type="checkbox"/> Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? <input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Competitive Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") <input type="checkbox"/> List of investors
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KER3 - OPERAS portfolio of services

Horizon Results Platform

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	OPERAS portfolio of services
*Message / Teaser to potential user	OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research. There are three types of services provided by OPERAS: Managed, Community and Internal. These services can be grouped into seven categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Training, and Operational and Collaboration Tools.
*Video/Image	

*Result type	<p>Select only 1</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify in the Result Description.</p>
*EU Missions	<p>Select any that apply</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Adaptation to climate change</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Cancer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Climate-neutral and smart cities</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Oceans, seas, and waters</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Soil health and food</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable</p>
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing from the</p>

<p>drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfill our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p>	
Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)
<input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
<input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
<input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended financing
<input type="checkbox"/> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential	<input type="checkbox"/> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations <input type="checkbox"/> Incubators / Accelerators <input type="checkbox"/> Marketing Mentoring or Coaching <input type="checkbox"/> Financing Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Technology Transfer Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Legal / IPR advise <input type="checkbox"/> I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party <input type="checkbox"/> Investor readiness training <input type="checkbox"/> Investor introductions <input type="checkbox"/> Business plan development <input type="checkbox"/> Expanding to more markets /finding new customers

		<input type="checkbox"/> Executive Training <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
	<input type="checkbox"/> Research and Technology Organisations	<input type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Academia/Universities	<input type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Private Investors	<input type="checkbox"/> Business Angels <input type="checkbox"/> Venture Capital <input type="checkbox"/> Crowd-funding Equity <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)	Increase usage/uptake of services; Financial support	

About us

Other related projects	COESO, TRIPLE
*Result Contributors	OPERAS AISBL, Ubiquity Press, Net7, Lexis, OAPEN, UC
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS AISBL
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description: Service Catalogue
	Link: https://operas-eu.org/services/
	Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, YouTube (will add)

	rows)
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Result Description and Influence

<p>*Result description (1200 characters max)</p>	<p>OPERAS offers a comprehensive approach to scholarly communication, supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research. There are three types of services provided by OPERAS: Managed, Community and Internal. These services can be grouped into seven categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Training, and Operational and Collaboration Tools.</p>			
<p>*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)</p>	<p>Please select up to three</p> <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and rural development <input type="checkbox"/> Banking and financial services <input type="checkbox"/> Better Regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Borders and security <input type="checkbox"/> Budget <input type="checkbox"/> Business and industry <input type="checkbox"/> Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Competition <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Culture and media <input type="checkbox"/> Customs <input type="checkbox"/> Defence <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Digital economy and society <input type="checkbox"/> Economy, finance and the euro <input type="checkbox"/> Education and training <input type="checkbox"/> Employment and social affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> EU enlargement <input type="checkbox"/> European </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign affairs and security policy <input type="checkbox"/> Fraud prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Home affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Humanitarian aid and civil protection <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional affairs <input type="checkbox"/> International Partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Justice and fundamental rights <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime affairs and fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> Migration and asylum <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Public health <input type="checkbox"/> Regional policy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research and innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Single market <input type="checkbox"/> Space <input type="checkbox"/> Sport <input type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation <input type="checkbox"/> Trade </td> </tr> </table>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and rural development <input type="checkbox"/> Banking and financial services <input type="checkbox"/> Better Regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Borders and security <input type="checkbox"/> Budget <input type="checkbox"/> Business and industry <input type="checkbox"/> Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Competition <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Culture and media <input type="checkbox"/> Customs <input type="checkbox"/> Defence <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Digital economy and society <input type="checkbox"/> Economy, finance and the euro <input type="checkbox"/> Education and training <input type="checkbox"/> Employment and social affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> EU enlargement <input type="checkbox"/> European 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign affairs and security policy <input type="checkbox"/> Fraud prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Home affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Humanitarian aid and civil protection <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional affairs <input type="checkbox"/> International Partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Justice and fundamental rights <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime affairs and fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> Migration and asylum <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Public health <input type="checkbox"/> Regional policy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research and innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Single market <input type="checkbox"/> Space <input type="checkbox"/> Sport <input type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation <input type="checkbox"/> Trade
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	neighbourhood policy <input type="checkbox"/> Food safety	<input type="checkbox"/> Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Youth
*Tags / Keywords	SSH, Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Training, Collaboration Tools, Metrics, Peer-Review, Diamond, Open Access, Publishing, Citizen Science	
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Goal 1: No poverty <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 2: Zero hunger <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 4: Quality education <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 5: Gender equality <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 10: Reducing inequalities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 13: Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 14: Life below water <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 15: Life on land <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	
Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	Please select one
	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) <input type="checkbox"/> 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5)

This project has received funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101079608. The content of this deliverable reflects only the OPERAS's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) <input type="checkbox"/> 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - Market Deployment <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	All services have recently moved from a variety of development phases into production. Moving forward, we are shifting our focus towards marketing and sustainability. This transition brings about exciting opportunities for growth and expansion. However, it also poses challenges, particularly in ensuring the long-term sustainability of our services.
Do you already have customers for this result?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	A comprehensive approach supporting the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enabling greater community control over openness and accessibility.
Do you have a scalable business model?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	Though it would be a challenge for organisations to copy what has been done, there is an opportunity to replicate a couple services in terms of offering a white label solution.
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	OPERAS Research Infrastructure provides a sustainable structure for managing the service portfolio in the long-term. However, ensuring the long-term financing is still under discussion alongside the preparations to become an ERIC. Current financial commitments are on an annual basis. Some project funding will need to be sought in order to bridge the gap.
Are you targeting geographical	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

markets?	
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.

Investors Corner

*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?	<p>Please select one</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <100K</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 101-500K</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 501K-1M</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1M-2.5M</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2.6M-5M</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5.1M-10M</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> >10M</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No investment sought</p>
I can provide the following upon request by an interested party	<p>Select any that apply</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Short presentation(s)</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Case study(ies)</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Related Technology white paper</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Complete and detailed business plan</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Market study with:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><input type="checkbox"/> If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements?</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Assessment</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative Assessment</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Competitive Assessment</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline")</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> List of investors</p>

KER4 - OPERAS user training framework

Horizon Results Platform

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Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	OPERAS User Engagement Initiative: Advancing Scholarly Communication and Open Science Training in SSH
*Message / Teaser to potential user	<p>"Empowering People in Open Science and Scholarly Communication"</p> <p>At the OPERAS User Engagement Initiative, our commitment lies in placing individuals at the forefront of our endeavours. Through various user-centred design methodologies, including participatory design, we tailor services to meet the distinctive requirements of the SSH community, setting a new standard for excellence in open science and scholarly communication. Our extensive training activities not only empower the OPERAS community but also engage a diverse audience across academic disciplines. This initiative plays a crucial role in building a connected, proficient scholarly ecosystem capable of adapting to the evolving landscape of open science. Join us or stay updated on our transformative journey as we enhance scholarly communication and open science, transcending conventional disciplinary boundaries with our insights and innovations.</p>
*Video/Image	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QeYZIHEPKrdbkHCzUfwjuMMrByFhXzY/view
*Result type	<p>Select only 1</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.</p>

	<input type="checkbox"/> ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.										
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other Intangible Results – (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know how, best practices, methodologies etc.)										
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Services – (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.);										
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify in the Result Description.										
*EU Missions	Select any that apply <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Adaptation to climate change <input type="checkbox"/> Cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Climate-neutral and smart cities <input type="checkbox"/> Oceans, seas, and waters <input type="checkbox"/> Soil health and food <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not applicable 										
*Target audiences and Needs	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing to from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfill our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left; padding: 5px;">Target audiences (up to 3)</th> <th style="text-align: left; padding: 5px;">Our Needs (any that apply)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers</td> <td style="padding: 5px;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;"><input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)</td> <td style="padding: 5px;"><input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions</td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended financing </td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 5px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential</td> <td style="padding: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations <input type="checkbox"/> Incubators / Accelerators </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy	<input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy	<input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions	<input type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended financing	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential	<input type="checkbox"/> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations <input type="checkbox"/> Incubators / Accelerators
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Private Investors	<input type="checkbox"/> Business Angels <input type="checkbox"/> Venture Capital <input type="checkbox"/> Crowd-funding Equity <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for	We're reaching out to potential collaborators within and beyond OPERAS to strengthen user engagement and training efforts in open science and scholarly communication. Our main objective is to gather valuable insights and best practices from OPERAS and	

(600 characters max)	<p>apply them effectively. Our focus includes the development of user-centred design (UCD) and user experience (UX) resources, such as best practice guides and toolkits, with a strong emphasis on skill enhancement and training for existing scholarly communication services. Additionally, we are dedicated to creating FAIR-compliant learning materials. Partners interested in tackling challenges in digital transformation and innovation within scholarly communication are crucial to our mission. User engagement initiatives are pivotal to our goals. Moreover, we are actively seeking collaboration to establish a comprehensive registry of training materials, incorporating all relevant resources in open scholarly communication and publishing.</p>
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About us

Other related projects	
*Result Contributors	UNIZD, OPERAS AISBL, UNITO, AMU, Lexis, Net7, OAPEN, Ubiquity Press
*Owners for exploitation	OPERAS AISBL
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Logo	
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description:
	Link:
	(add others)

Result Description and Influence

*Result description (1200 characters max)	<p>The OPERAS User Engagement Initiative aims to transform the user experience and training in open science and scholarly communication, focusing on the SSH community. This effort integrates user-centred design (UCD) and user experience (UX) methodologies into OPERAS services, aiming to uplift the quality of scholarly communication and open science practices. Central to this initiative is the collaborative development of best practice guides, toolkits, and in-depth training</p>
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	<p>programmes. Emphasising practical application, including usability testing and participatory design, ensures OPERAS services are intuitive and accessible, meeting diverse scholarly needs. The initiative is ready to reduce barriers in digital transformation and prompt innovation, equipping users with vital skills and knowledge for the changing landscape of scholarly communication. This endeavour augments the capabilities within the OPERAS community and aspires to set new standards of excellence in open science and scholarly communication across disciplines.</p>			
<p>*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)</p>	<p>Please select up to three</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="485 792 1369 1921"> <tr> <td data-bbox="485 792 928 1921"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and rural development <input type="checkbox"/> Banking and financial services <input type="checkbox"/> Better Regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Borders and security <input type="checkbox"/> Budget <input type="checkbox"/> Business and industry <input type="checkbox"/> Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Competition <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Culture and media <input type="checkbox"/> Customs <input type="checkbox"/> Defence <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Digital economy and society <input type="checkbox"/> Economy, finance and the euro <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education and training <input type="checkbox"/> Employment and social affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> EU enlargement </td> <td data-bbox="928 792 1369 1921"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign affairs and security policy <input type="checkbox"/> Fraud prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Home affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Humanitarian aid and civil protection <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional affairs <input type="checkbox"/> International Partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Justice and fundamental rights <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime affairs and fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> Migration and asylum <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Public health <input type="checkbox"/> Regional policy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research and innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Single market <input type="checkbox"/> Space <input type="checkbox"/> Sport <input type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation </td> </tr> </table>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and rural development <input type="checkbox"/> Banking and financial services <input type="checkbox"/> Better Regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Borders and security <input type="checkbox"/> Budget <input type="checkbox"/> Business and industry <input type="checkbox"/> Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Competition <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Culture and media <input type="checkbox"/> Customs <input type="checkbox"/> Defence <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Digital economy and society <input type="checkbox"/> Economy, finance and the euro <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education and training <input type="checkbox"/> Employment and social affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> EU enlargement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign affairs and security policy <input type="checkbox"/> Fraud prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Home affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Humanitarian aid and civil protection <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional affairs <input type="checkbox"/> International Partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Justice and fundamental rights <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime affairs and fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> Migration and asylum <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Public health <input type="checkbox"/> Regional policy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research and innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Single market <input type="checkbox"/> Space <input type="checkbox"/> Sport <input type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation
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	<input type="checkbox"/> European neighbourhood policy <input type="checkbox"/> Food safety	<input type="checkbox"/> Trade <input type="checkbox"/> Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Youth
*Tags / Keywords	Open science Scholarly communication Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) User engagement User-centred Design (UCD) User experience (UX) methodologies Participatory design Training programs Skill development	
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 1: No poverty <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 2: Zero hunger <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 4: Quality education <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 5: Gender equality <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 10: Reducing inequalities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 13: Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 14: Life below water <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 15: Life on land <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable 	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	

Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Text
	Title:	Title:
	Link:	Description:

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2) <input type="checkbox"/> 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3) <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6) <input type="checkbox"/> 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8) <input type="checkbox"/> 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9) <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - Market Deployment <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	<p>In its initial year, KER4 focused on developing the UCQ-FRAME for user engagement evaluation with OPERAS services alongside a UX maturity questionnaire. The next steps involve implementing and testing this framework with selected services to enhance its efficacy. Parallely, we'll develop the OPERAS skills and training framework, iteratively refining user research methodologies and evaluating UX maturity. Upcoming phases also include scholarly contributions and global outreach through events like OpenUX Meetup, with UCQ-FRAME as a guiding playbook.</p>
Do you already have customers for this result?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	<p>OPERAS offers a unique value in enhancing scholarly communication through user-centred design and advanced training in open science. Our methodological framework, UCQ-FRAME, and tailored training programs specifically address the evolving needs of the SSH community. These tools and strategies aim to elevate user engagement, making scholarly processes more intuitive, accessible, and aligned with modern</p>

	research practices.
Do you have a scalable business model?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	<p>KER4's replicability is anchored in its adaptable and transferable methodologies. Central to this is the UCQ-FRAME, a framework developed not solely for a specific OPERAS project but with broader applicability across various scholarly communication contexts. This framework demonstrates flexibility in evaluating user engagement and experience, suitable for diverse settings. Its integration into new proposals and the ability to build upon best practices from various OPERAS projects further showcase its replicability. While the comprehensive training program focusing on open science and FAIR principles is still in the planning stages, the foundational work of KER4 lays the groundwork for future scalable and adaptable training initiatives. These elements collectively enhance the utility of OPERAS services and set a replicable standard for user-centred design in scholarly communication, presenting a model for similar open science initiatives.</p>
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	<p>The initiative's focus on user-centred design and open science principles positions it as a valuable asset in the scholarly world, attracting ongoing interest and support. Moreover, OPERAS's commitment to developing methodologies like UCQ-FRAME and training programs ensures its relevance and applicability in various contexts, crucial for sustained engagement and utility. The initiative's ability to adapt to changing technological and</p>

	scholarly landscapes further enhances its long-term viability. By continuously updating its practices and expanding its reach within the scholarly community, OPERAS remains at the forefront of innovation in scholarly communication, ensuring its ongoing relevance and sustainability.
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.
	Europe (open and inclusive approach, welcoming collaboration and engagement from the global scholarly community)

Investors Corner

*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?	Please select one
	<input type="checkbox"/> <100K <input type="checkbox"/> 101-500K <input type="checkbox"/> 501K-1M <input type="checkbox"/> 1M-2.5M <input type="checkbox"/> 2.6M-5M <input type="checkbox"/> 5.1M-10M <input type="checkbox"/> >10M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No investment sought
I can provide the following upon request by an interested party	Select any that apply
	<input type="checkbox"/> Short presentation(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Case study(ies) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Related Technology white paper <input type="checkbox"/> A reference list of business partners, employers and/or collaborators <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) <input type="checkbox"/> A list of IPR - patents (pending or

	<p>granted) and academic papers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Complete and detailed business plan <input type="checkbox"/> Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Competitive Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") <input type="checkbox"/> List of investors
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KER5 - OPERAS national nodes

Horizon Results Platform

Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs

*Title of Result	Establishment of a roadmap for the OPERAS national nodes
*Message / Teaser to potential user	The set up of a roadmap has been agreed by all partners involved in the OPERAS-PLUS project and reviewed by external experts. Its utility is self-evident as a means for putting into practice activities to be carried out in nodes in all contexts and with different levels of funding and engagement. The purpose to make it public is to provide tools for other projects to implement their own nodes using this basis and adapting for their own realities. Our target audiences are all scientific communities and research infrastructures, especially those focused in the SSH.
*Video/Image	https://youtu.be/xfOVAJfPNpk
*Result type	Select only 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Related Result - Result primarily useful and influential for policy makers or legislators (Ex. regulatory analysis, policy related study, foresight analysis, pre-standard, standard, publications of other forms, etc.). <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific or Technological R&D Result including ICT Hardware – Any scientific or technological R&D related

	<p>result at any stage of development. The results can be a scientific finding or approach, model or method, a proof of concept, a technological solution or component, a chemical, a new material, a new manufacturing process, a medicine, a therapy, an agri-food, an electric component, sensor, processor, computer hardware, etc. The result can be at any stage of development: from the basic, applied research to the prototype and commercial readiness.</p>					
	<p><input type="checkbox"/> ICT Software Digital solution – Any software, algorithm, database, model, online platform, cloud, etc. at any stage of development.</p>					
	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Other Intangible Results - (Ex. citizens engagement platform, know-how, best practices, methodologies etc.)</p>					
	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Services - (Ex. research infrastructures, educational sources, citizen helplines, etc.).</p>					
	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify in the Result Description.</p>					
<p>*EU Missions</p>	<p>Select any that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Adaptation to climate change <input type="checkbox"/> Cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Climate-neutral and smart cities <input type="checkbox"/> Oceans, seas, and waters <input type="checkbox"/> Soil health and food <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable 					
<p>*Target audiences and Needs</p>	<p>The “target audience” automatically triggers a varying set of needs for the “Our needs are” section therefore they must be directly linked, and the specific list chosen from.</p> <p>Select the audience(s) you are addressing to from the drop-down menu, you may select up to three (3). In case you selected Policy Related Result as type, you will not see "Other Actors who can help us fulfill our market potential" nor "Private Investors".</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="430 1742 1369 1910"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="430 1742 912 1787">Target audiences (up to 3)</th> <th data-bbox="912 1742 1369 1787">Our Needs (any that apply)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="430 1787 912 1910"> <input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers </td> <td data-bbox="912 1787 1369 1910"> <input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)	<input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
Target audiences (up to 3)	Our Needs (any that apply)					
<input type="checkbox"/> EU and Member State Policy-makers	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy					

	<input type="checkbox"/> International Organisations (ex. OECD, FAO, UN, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> To raise awareness and possibly influence policy
	<input type="checkbox"/> Public or private funding institutions	<input type="checkbox"/> Grants and Subsidies <input type="checkbox"/> Loans <input type="checkbox"/> Loan guarantees <input type="checkbox"/> Other blended financing
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Actors who can help us fulfil our market potential	<input type="checkbox"/> Business partners - SMEs, Entrepreneurs, Large Corporations <input type="checkbox"/> Incubators / Accelerators <input type="checkbox"/> Marketing Mentoring or Coaching <input type="checkbox"/> Financing Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Technology Transfer Expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Legal / IPR advise <input type="checkbox"/> I/we wish to transfer my/our IPR to an interested party <input type="checkbox"/> Investor readiness training <input type="checkbox"/> Investor introductions <input type="checkbox"/> Business plan development <input type="checkbox"/> Expanding to more markets /finding new customers <input type="checkbox"/> Executive Training <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
	<input type="checkbox"/> Research and Technology Organisations	<input type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure

		<input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Academia/Universities	<input type="checkbox"/> Help in technical expertise <input type="checkbox"/> Use of research Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration
	<input type="checkbox"/> Private Investors	<input type="checkbox"/> Business Angels <input type="checkbox"/> Venture Capital <input type="checkbox"/> Crowd-funding Equity <input type="checkbox"/> Other type of Investment
*We specifically need/ are looking for (600 characters max)	We are looking for collaborations with research communities and research infrastructures engaged in developing stronger national communities of SSH scholarly communication in the European Research Area.	

About us

Other related projects	OPERAS-GER, OPERAS-PL
*Result Contributors	Fundación Española para la Ciencia y Tecnología, F.S.P. (FECYT) CNRS—OpenEdition Max Weber Stiftung National Documentation Centre (EKT) University of Zadar CNR-ILIESI OAPEN Foundation ERIH PLUS Institute of Literary Research Polish Academy of Sciences University of Coimbra The Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU) Jisc
*Owners for exploitation	
Start-up created for further exploitation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Logo	Available at:

	https://operas-eu.org/operas-national-nodes/
Testimonials	Title:
	Link:
Find us on	Description: Websites/blogs of the funded national nodes
	Link: https://operas-ger.hypotheses.org
	https://operas.pl

Result Description and Influence

*Result description (1200 characters max)	National nodes play a pivotal role in establishing a connection point to outside the OPERAS community, in promoting a proximity relation with local communities, helping to identify needs, provide services, and training. They are in a decisive position to find a balanced solution for the keeping of national languages as fully scientific valid modes of expression, while promoting them on the international level.	
*Business Sector(s)/ Policy Area(s)	Please select up to three	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture and rural development <input type="checkbox"/> Banking and financial services <input type="checkbox"/> Better Regulation <input type="checkbox"/> Borders and security <input type="checkbox"/> Budget <input type="checkbox"/> Business and industry <input type="checkbox"/> Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Competition <input type="checkbox"/> Consumers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Culture and media <input type="checkbox"/> Customs <input type="checkbox"/> Defence <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Digital economy and society <input type="checkbox"/> Economy, finance and the euro	<input type="checkbox"/> Foreign affairs and security policy <input type="checkbox"/> Fraud prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Home affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Humanitarian aid and civil protection <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional affairs <input type="checkbox"/> International Partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Justice and fundamental rights <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime affairs and fisheries <input type="checkbox"/> Migration and asylum <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Public health <input type="checkbox"/> Regional policy

	<input type="checkbox"/> Education and training <input type="checkbox"/> Employment and social affairs <input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> EU enlargement <input type="checkbox"/> European neighbourhood policy <input type="checkbox"/> Food safety	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research and innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Single market <input type="checkbox"/> Space <input type="checkbox"/> Sport <input type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Taxation <input type="checkbox"/> Trade <input type="checkbox"/> Transport <input type="checkbox"/> Youth
*Tags / Keywords	Scholarly communication; multilingualism; bibliodiversity; open science; national communities	
*Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals	Please select up to three <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 1: No poverty <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 2: Zero hunger <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 3: Good health and well-being for people <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 4: Quality education <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 5: Gender equality <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 10: Reducing inequalities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 13: Climate action <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 14: Life below water <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 15: Life on land <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Goal 17: Partnerships for the goals <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	
Has your result had or you expect it to have significant influence on policy-making?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	

Other information / data to share (Link or text)	Can add multiple pieces of information and multiple types	
	Link	Link
	Title: D7.1 – Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes	Title: Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS National Nodes
	Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10725785	Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289238

Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook

*Results Maturity	<p>Please select one</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 - R&D - Basic technology Research (TRL1-2)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 - R&D - Research for Feasibility (TRL 2-3)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3 - R&D Technology Development (TRL 3-5)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4 - R&D Technology Demonstration (TRL 5-6)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 - Demonstration - System Development (TRL 6-8)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 6 - Demonstration - System Launch and Operations (TRL 8-9)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 7 - Market Deployment</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not applicable</p>
*Current Stage and Next Steps (400 characters max)	<p>Currently, partners have presented a background of the work undergone by current OPERAS national nodes, an overview of the commonalities and differences between the work of the diverse nodes. They approached the challenges and opportunities presented as well, to find a common ground in which it is possible to establish common requirements for all, including issues regarding the building of the national nodes, sustainability and the positioning of OPERAS national nodes both nationally and at the European level.</p>
Do you already have customers for this result?	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
*Unique value proposition (400 characters max)	<p>To provide a means of coordination to the OPERAS Research Infrastructure national nodes and to support them with training materials, communication</p>

	coordination and governance.
Do you have a scalable business model?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	
Is your result replicable?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	It can be adapted to other research infrastructures and projects.
Is your result and your business model sustainable in the long-term?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, must elaborate (1000 characters max)	Our result is built to be sustained in different funding and research contexts and in many geographical locations.
Are you targeting geographical markets?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes, what are the main geographical markets you are targeting?	Drop down list of global regions as well as individual countries, just list the regions initially, unless there are specific countries to highlight, can do the mapping after.
	Spain France Germany Greece Croatia Finland Italy Netherlands Norway Poland Portugal Slovenia UK

Investors Corner

<p>*What level of investment (EUR) are you currently looking for?</p>	<p>Please select one</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> <100K <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 101-500K <input type="checkbox"/> 501K-1M <input type="checkbox"/> 1M-2.5M <input type="checkbox"/> 2.6M-5M <input type="checkbox"/> 5.1M-10M <input type="checkbox"/> >10M <input type="checkbox"/> No investment sought
<p>I can provide the following upon request by an interested party</p>	<p>Select any that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Short presentation(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Detailed description(s) / Presentation(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Case study(ies) <input type="checkbox"/> Related Technology white paper <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> A reference list of business partners, employers and/ or collaborators <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective business partners (including suppliers) <input type="checkbox"/> A list of IPR - patents (pending or granted) and academic papers <input type="checkbox"/> Complete and detailed business plan <input type="checkbox"/> Market study with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> If yes, or under preparation, does it contain the following elements? <input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Competitive Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> List of current and prospective clients ("pipeline") <input type="checkbox"/> List of investors

